

Guideline / Checklist

The use of generative AI in research needs to align with the principles and responsibilities outlined in the *Australian Code for the Responsible Conduct of Research* 2018. Guidelines about the appropriate disclosure and documentation to accompany the use of Generative AI in research also need to recognise the practical considerations of current or innovative research practices. An approach combining these elements is detailed below for Macquarie University researchers:

1. **Researchers must align the use of generative AI and their reporting of such use with the Principles and Responsibilities specified in the *Australian Code for the Responsible Conduct of Research*:**

Principle 2: Rigour in Research:

To ensure rigour in the development, undertaking and reporting of research using generative AI tools, researchers must:

- Ensure that the use of generative AI is permitted in the relevant ethics protocols (including participant consent), funding agreements, target journal guidelines, and third-party research arrangements.
- Document specific generative AI models, including their version, parameters, and prompts used. If a model itself has been customised (“fine-tuned”), the fine-tuning data and mechanisms must be preserved.
- Address potential biases in AI systems, by thoughtfully constructing system and user prompts, and testing the models before applying real data for inference.
- Ensure robust, documented, and reproducible methodology in AI-assisted research processes.
- Safeguard sensitive information and managing risks, making sure that account compromise will not reveal sensitive information, ensuring that models will not use or retain data for “training”, and ensuring that the terms of service of the Model provider are compatible with Macquarie University Policy and Australian laws.
- Critically evaluate the output and take full responsibility for the logic, reasoning and validity of the content.

Principle 3: Transparency in Research

To ensure the use of Generative AI in research methodology, data and findings is openly, responsibly and accurately recorded, researchers should:

- Clearly record how and why generative AI was used in the research.
- Openly communicate how generative AI was integrated into the research process.
- Share user and system prompts, AI-generated inference, outputs, and the documentation and evidence of the validation methods applied.

Responsibility 22: Record Keeping

Because generative AI outputs can vary even with identical inputs, maintaining comprehensive records is essential. To enable research reproducibility and verification, researchers should:

- Retain dated logs of generative AI interactions and prompts.
- Document post-processing of AI-generated content.
- Ensure records are secure, complete, and accessible where appropriate.

2. To facilitate appropriate disclosure and documentation to accompany outputs reporting research which utilised Generative AI, researchers should:

- Follow publisher, funder, AI provider, and institutional instructions for disclosure.
- Tailor disclosure to the extent and context of AI use, for example:
 - Extensive use: Provide detailed appendix or supplementary document detailing the tools employed, prompts used, and post-generation editing undertaken.
 - Moderate use: Describe in the methods section or relevant areas of the main text. Provide prompts and outputs used in the supplementary data.
 - Limited use (for example their use in editing or addition of phrases or sentences): Use a footnote or general disclaimers and provide prompts used in supplementary data.
 - Avoid using the acknowledgments section for AI disclosure, as listing third parties in this section generally implies their ethical agreement, intellectual contribution, or other types of support for the research.

Consider key elements to include in the disclosure, including:

- Specific generative AI tools used: Clearly state which generative AI tools, services or models were employed (e.g., claude-3.7-sonnet-20250219 or 01-2024-12-17, Interface (Claude.ai, ChatGPT.com, specific source code with link), and where to find the prompt and output logs (e.g. an OSF, Figshare, or Zenodo repository).
- Extent of generative AI involvement: Describe and document the precise role generative AI played in the research process, such as data analysis, literature review, or hypothesis generation.
- Methodology: Explain why and how generative AI was used, including any prompts, parameters, or fine-tuning applied to the model.
- Limitations: Acknowledge potential biases or limitations of the generative AI system and how these were critically explored and addressed.
- Human oversight: Clarify the level of human review and validation of AI-generated content.
- Ethical considerations: Address any ethical implications of using generative AI in the research context, including the potential for bias and confabulation.
- Reproducibility: Provide sufficient details to allow other researchers to replicate the generative AI-assisted portions of the research where appropriate.
- Intellectual Property (IP) compliance: When generating images, videos, or voice content, ensure adequate legal arrangements encompassing fair treatment of artists and respect for IP rights. If you are sourcing voice or images to clone or generate voice, images, or videos, you must obtain the artist's approval for the intended use case.

